

Temperature Control System for IOT-based Banana Chips Fryer Machine to Increase Productivity in Gelumpang Payong Village, Jeumpa District, Bireuen Regency

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Abstract – Vacuum Frying is a new technology that can be used to determine the quality of frying by using a vacuum. This study aims to determine and examine the effect of temperature on cooking oil and frying time on chemical and organoleptic properties of banana chips in order to obtain the best quality product. The quality parameters tested included moisture content, fat content, color, thickness and organoleptic tests. Banana chips are fried in oil at temperatures of 60, 70, 80, and 90 ° C and frying times of 30, 45, 60 and 75 minutes. The best quality of banana chips was obtained at 80 ° C for 60 minutes. Aluminum foil can maintain the shelf life of banana chips for 120 days of storage. It is indicated that the temperature and frying time significantly affect the quality and characteristics of the product.

Keywords: Design, Machine, Vacuum Frying, IoT

Introduction

Vacuum Frying is a production machine for frying various kinds of fruits and vegetables by frying using a vacuum. Frying using a vacuum is the right processing method to produce high quality chips and fruit [2]. This vacuum frying machine has the working principle of vacuum frying, namely sucking the water content in the bananas at high speed so that the pores of the fruit and vegetable flesh do not close quickly, so that the water content in the bananas can be absorbed perfectly. The working principle is to regulate the balance of temperature and pressure in a vacuum. In order to produce products with good quality in terms of color, aroma, as well as unchanged and crisp, the temperature setting should not exceed 90°C and the vacuum pressure is between 65 – 76 cmHg. We recommend that the water in the reservoir on the vacuum frying machine does not contain iron particles because it can cause turbid water and can damage the vacuum pump which ultimately affects the crispiness of the chips. Under vacuum conditions, the temperature in the frying machine can be lowered to 70-85°C due to the lowering of the boiling point of water. With this kind of frying system, food products that are damaged in frying (such as various fruits) so that the results can be fried properly, produce products that are dry and crunchy, without experiencing damage to nutritional value and flavor as is the case with ordinary frying [1]. Generally, low pressure frying will produce products with a crispier texture (drier), more attractive colors. Another important thing about vacuum frying products is that they contain less oil and are more porous (lighter) and generally have better rehydration power [3,4,6].

The factors that affect the final quality of the fried product are the quality of the ingredients that need to be fried and the quality of the cooking oil, the type of fryer and the packaging system for the final product[8,10]. During storage, fried products can be damaged, namely the occurrence of rancidity and changes in texture of the product [5]. Rancidity can occur because the oil/fat undergoes oxidation. This is influenced by the quality of the oil, the conditions of the frying process and the packaging system used.

Materials and Methods

The method used in this research is a real experimental method (true experimental research). This type of research aims to determine the suitable temperature for types of bananas and various fruits as well as the relationships that occur between existing factors or variables, by giving treatment to one or more experimental groups with different treatment conditions. The equipment needed to make banana chips includes Basin, swallowing mat, Slicer, Stainless steel knife, Plastic bucket, Frying pan, Vacuum Frying machine, Sealer, Furnace or stove or gas stove, Tampah/nyiru/container, Plastic container, Polypropylene (PP) plastic with a thickness of 0.8 mm/aluminum foil, Vacuum Frying Machine Label. A vacuum frying machine with a capacity 5 kg was used in this experiment.

1. Capacity (kg input / process): 5 kg
2. LPG fuel with automatic temperature control,
3. Water circulation cooling
4. Cooking oil volume: 40 liters,
5. Power requirements: 0.75 - 1 HP (600-750 watts)
6. Dimensions of the water tub: 180 x 120 x 60 cm.
7. Total dimensions: 180 x 120 x 120 cm

Figure 1. Tool specifications

The vacuum frying automation machine is a multipurpose chip fryer that is designed to make it easier for the operator during the frying process, and the design of this automatic system is made to control the vacuum process, cooking oil heating and draining time automatically which were previously controlled manually by the operator and require more time. so that this automation system can be more efficient.

The design of a series of vacuum frying automation system applications on a multipurpose chip fryer, starting from the planning process to the manufacture of circuit designs with component specifications are as follows:

Figure 2. Vacuum Frying Machine

The material inserted into a vacuum frying machine will be fried in a vacuum. This vacuum frying will make the water content in the fruit will be removed and replaced by oil. With an average frying temperature used around 70 - 90 °C and pressure can reach 76cmHg, with a frying duration between 30 minutes to 50 minutes (this treatment depends on the type and characteristics of the fruit). Because each fruit has different water content and texture. Because the frying with this vacuum frying machine can reduce the boiling point below 90 °C, the results of banana chips will not be charred. To fry the cooking oil requires about 12 liters. With the decrease

used to fry chips up to 100 times frying. Thus can save the use of cooking oil. For best results, it is proposed to use branded and clear cooking oil, because low quality cooking oil affect the color and aroma of fruit chips. Fruit made with this vacuum frying machine can last for consumption up to 4 to 5 months, and this also depends on the quality of the packaging.

This frying machine uses electronic circuits in devices such as temperature sensors found in digital thermostats to detect the temperature of cooking oil in the vacuum frying container tube. For the process of opening and closing the solenoid valve. The relay is used as a signal given by the IoT module to be forwarded to the solenoid valve. Solenoid valve is used to open and close the cooking oil tube pipeline, as well as opening and closing the gas flow on the stove. Timer delay relay is used to carry out the process of opening and closing the solenoid valve and the length of the draining process automatically, as well as the use of a fuse as a safety in the event of an electric current disturbance

Data collection

The steps or activities carried out in this study are design, where the phases in the design that will be carried out differ from one process to another.

Figure 3. Automatic System Design

Design of a temperature regulation system on a vacuum frying machine tool to determine the temperature of the type that is fried [9,10]. The first is to set the time for the banana chips frying process on the digital timer and set the temperature for the desired cooking oil on the digital thermostat and after everything has been set, the frying system process can start working. the first is to heat the cooking oil in the cooking oil container tube on the vacuum frying machine by using a gas stove under the oil tube (at this stage the solenoid valve 1 on the gas pipe opens because there is a signal from digital thermostat 1), then for the process heating the oil simultaneously with the ignition of the compressor on the vacuum frying machine by a digital timer which is continued by the relay, after the oil temperature has reached the desired digital thermostat 1 will cut off the signal

to the relay so that solenoid valve 1 will close the gas flow, then simultaneously timer 1 will give signal to solenoid valve 3 to open the inlet pipe on the cooking oil line which will flow to the frying tube. to fry on the raw material, you want to fry.

Table 1. Temperature Frying temperature using vacuum frying

Initial Chip Weigh	Frying temperature	Frying temperature	Chip Weight	Chip Criteria
5 kg	80	98 Minute	1.7 kg	All right, Crispy
5 kg	85	96 Minute	1.6 kg	All right, Crispy
5 kg	90	94 Minute	1.6 kg	All right, Crispy
5 kg	95	90 Minute	1.5 kg	All right, Crispy
5 kg	100	86 Minute	1.5 kg	All right, Crispy

Results

This study was conducted to determine the effect of temperature and duration of frying on quality and organoleptic parameters, as well as determining optimal temperature and frying time.

Figure 4. Graph of the Effect of Temperature and Frying Time

Figure 4 shows the effect of temperature on the frying system in three treatments with two repetitions. The study used 2 factors, namely temperature and frying time with three replications. The temperature factor has 3 levels, namely 70 °C, 80 °C and 90 °C. The time factor also has 3 levels, namely 30 minutes, 40 minutes and 50 minutes.

Figure 5. Graph of the Effect of Temperature and Crispness

Crispness is a parameter that is often used in assessing the texture of dry food products [11,12], according to surveys crispness is the main assessment factor in determining the quality of chips. The crispness score of the vacuum fried muli banana chips was 3.1 – 4.1, which means that the crispness of the chips produced ranged from slightly crunchy to crunchy [5]. Based on the results of the analysis of variance, it can be seen in Figure 5 that the concentration of CaCl_2 and the soaking time did not significantly affect the crispness of the vacuum fried muli banana chips.

The temperature in the results of this study determines the crispiness of the fryer at 90 °C for 50 minutes, while the lowest temperature is found in the product with a temperature of 70 °C for 30 minutes. The higher the temperature that is set and the frying time, the better the taste of the chips. In the aroma parameter, the highest temperature is also found at 90 °C for 50 minutes, and the lowest temperature is in the frying pan with a temperature of 70 °C for 30 minutes. As for color, it can be seen in the graph that the values for all treatments are not much different, and for crispness, the highest value is found in products treated with frying at 90 °C for 50 minutes. While the lowest was found in the treatment with a temperature of 70 °C for 30 minutes. From the Figure, it shows that the higher the temperature and frying time, the higher the crispness rating. This is in accordance with the value of the water content in the raw material. Where the lower the water content, the results of the frying are more crispy.

Conclusion

From the results of the application system design on a vacuum frying machine, there are still many existing vacuum fryers (using vacuum) that use manual vacuum fryers where no one has used them automatically. In this study, IoT-based temperature settings are used using electronic circuits such as digital thermostats with temperature sensors to determine and regulate the temperature in the frying system, solenoid valves to open and close the oil and gas flow pipes and timers to set the time required during the frying process and are also equipped with a contactor as a connector and an electric circuit breaker. The best temperature treatment and frying time for making banana chips is 90 °C for 50 minutes.

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